

LLM-Assisted Inductive Categorization: A Step-by-step guide

by Clarissa Sabrina Arlinghaus

Bielefeld University, Bielefeld, Germany, clarissa_sabrina.arlinghaus@uni-bielefeld.de

Thank you for your interest in LLM-Assisted Inductive Categorization (LAIC). LAIC is a method for qualitative research that uses a Large Language Model (LLM) to form inductive categories and assign them to text statements. We developed and evaluated this method. You can find the preprint here: <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/gpnye>

The following pages provide detailed instructions on using the LAIC templates in Python editors. Don't worry if you're not familiar with Python or if the code looks complicated at first glance. You don't need to fully understand every line of code. Instead, focus on making specific adjustments as instructed, while many parts of the code can remain unchanged. This guide will walk you through everything step by step. No programming knowledge is necessary.

All files should be stored in a dedicated folder. There is no need to save them all at once, as this guide will provide the necessary links at each step. You can follow along incrementally.

When working with file names, I recommend leaving them as they are initially and making changes only afterward if necessary. Furthermore, it is crucial to pay careful attention to quotation marks and file extensions when making any changes in the templates.

If you have any more questions, please contact Clarissa Sabrina Arlinghaus (clarissa_sabrina.arlinghaus@uni-bielefeld.de).

This guide is divided into three main parts:

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Step 0: Preparations

In step 0, we will ensure that all necessary preparations are made to successfully carry out LAIC. Once these preparations are complete, you will be ready to move on to step 1, where we will form the inductive categories.

0.1 Installing Python and a Python Editor

Step 0.1 explains how to install Python and a Python editor on your computer free of charge. This is a necessary preparation to be able to perform LAIC with the Python templates. If you have already installed Python and a Python editor on your computer, you can skip step 0.1.

0.1.1 Download and install Python

- Please visit the official Python website: <https://www.python.org/>
- Click on the "Downloads" button. There, you will find the latest version of Python for various operating systems.
- Please download the latest version of Python for your operating system. If you are unsure about which version to choose, choose the recommended option. The version you should install is displayed directly. I've provided an example from a Windows laptop on the left and an iMac on the right. In both cases, the recommended version is highlighted in yellow text. While I was writing this guide, Python 3.12.5 was the latest version, but don't be surprised if there's a newer version by the time you read this. Just go ahead and download the latest one.

- Open the downloaded installation file. Check your "Downloads" folder if you cannot find the file.
- *For Windows users:* Check the box next to "Add python.exe to PATH". This makes it easier to use Python via the command line. Then, click on "Install Now" to start the installation process. Wait until the installation is complete. After the installation is complete, you can close the installation program.

- For macOS users: Follow the installation program instructions until the installation is complete. You can leave the default settings as they are and simply proceed through the installation wizard. Simply keep clicking "Continue" (in German: "Fortfahren") throughout the installation process, except for one point where you need to accept the license agreement. At that step, be sure to click "Accept" (in German: "Akzeptieren"). Don't be confused that parts of the screenshot are in German. On your Mac, these parts (e.g., the name of the buttons) will appear in the language you have set for your system. After the installation is complete, you can close the installation program (in German: "Schließen") and move the installation program to the trash.

0.1.2 Download and install a Python editor

- There are different Python editors out there. You are free to choose any of them. However, I recommend using Visual Studio Code because it is free and suitable for beginners. Therefore, this guide describes the procedure for installing and using Visual Studio Code.
- Please visit the official website of Visual Studio Code: <https://code.visualstudio.com/Download>
- Please download the version that is suitable for your operating system (e.g., Windows, Linux, macOS).

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Download Visual Studio Code

Free and built on open source. Integrated Git, debugging and extensions.

Windows users click here

OS	Architecture	File Type
Windows	x64	User Installer
		System Installer
	ARM64	Installer
		CLI
Linux (Debian, Ubuntu)	x64	.deb
		.rpm
	ARM64	.tar.gz
		Snap
Mac (macOS 10.15+)	Intel chip	Apple silicon
		Universal
	Apple silicon	CLI
		CLI

macOS users click here

By downloading and using Visual Studio Code, you agree to the [license terms](#) and [privacy statement](#).

- Open the downloaded installation file. Check your "Downloads" folder if you cannot find the file.
- Follow the installation program instructions until the installation is complete. Make sure to check the box for "I accept the license agreements" (in German: "Ich akzeptiere die Vereinbarung") to agree to the term. You can leave the default settings as they are and simply proceed through the installation wizard by clicking further (in German: "Weiter") until it finishes. Creating a desktop link (in German: "Desktop-Symbol erstellen") is not mandatory, but it is highly recommended. Don't be confused that the provided screenshot are in German. On your computer, these texts will appear in the language you have set for your system. Also, don't be surprised if the installation process looks a bit different on your system. On my Mac, I could simply click the program and only had to confirm once that I trusted the application from the internet. After that, it was already installed. On the other hand, with my Windows laptop, I had to click through the installation wizard as depicted in the screenshot. The installation steps vary depending on the operating system, but rest assured, Visual Studio Code works equally well on both Windows and Mac. Visual Studio Code also works on Linux, although I did not test this.

Start Visual Studio Code. You can click on the desktop link. If you did not create a desktop link, you may find Visual Studio Code under your installed programs or downloads.

- Click on the square icon on the left sidebar to open the extension manager.

- Type **Python** in the search bar and press Enter.
- Click on "Install" for the Python extension from Microsoft. Don't be confused by the various options; just choose Python without any additions. If asked, use the release version. Note: Even if you're using a Mac, you'll need to install the Python extension from Microsoft in Visual Studio Code to ensure everything works correctly.

0.2 Obtaining an OpenAI API key

To use LAIC, you will need an API key from a service provider that offers Large Language Model capabilities. Follow the provider's instructions to sign up and obtain your API key. In this guide, we will work specifically with the OpenAI API key, as OpenAI is the company behind the LLM models we will be using (i.e., GPT-4o). Therefore, we provide instructions on how to obtain an OpenAI API key. If you wish to use models from other providers, you may need to obtain API keys from those companies instead. Make sure to keep your API key secure, as it will be necessary for accessing the LLM.

0.2.1 OpenAI API Key

- To create inductive categories with LLMs from OpenAI (e.g., GPT-4o), you need an OpenAI API key. If you do not yet have an OpenAI API key, you can register on OpenAI and apply for an OpenAI API key.
- A tutorial on how to get an OpenAI API key can be found here: <https://platform.openai.com/docs/quickstart>

0.2.2 OpenAI API Pricing

- Your OpenAI API key is your personal access code that is used to bill your usage (e.g., through your credit card). Do not give your OpenAI API key to other people. Otherwise, you will be charged for the resources they use with your OpenAI API key.
- Information about the current prices of OpenAI models can be found at <https://openai.com/api/pricing/>.
- OpenAI determines the costs and sets its prices independently. I am not affiliated with their pricing. I am providing the LAIC templates and this guide free of charge to make LAIC more accessible. I do not receive any compensation from OpenAI for this.
- You can estimate the approximate costs for performing step 1 and step 2 of LAIC in step 0.3. An OpenAI API Key is not required to use the cost calculator provided in step 0.3

0.2.3 OpenAI API Key Possibilities

- Once you have obtained an OpenAI API key, you can use it many times. You do not need a new OpenAI API key each time. You can perform both steps of LAIC with the same OpenAI API key. Even if you wish to perform LAIC at a later date, you can generally continue to use the same OpenAI API key. Therefore, obtaining an OpenAI key is a worthwhile investment.
- Additionally, you can use the same OpenAI API key for other tasks, such as generating AI images. If you are interested in learning how to generate AI images in Python and R, please refer to our tutorial (Arlinghaus & Maier, 2024c).
- Although getting an OpenAI Key may initially seem cumbersome or annoying, it pays off in the long run.
- I am not affiliated with OpenAI. I do not receive any financial or non-financial benefits for recommending their API keys.

0.3 Calculating Costs

You may want to estimate the cost of performing LAIC beforehand. That is free of charge and possible, even if you do not yet obtain an OpenAI API key. This is optional. If you are not interested in a cost estimate, you can proceed directly to step 1. For those who do wish to estimate costs, keep reading the next steps.

0.3.1 Cost factors

- The cost depends on various factors, namely the number of API calls, models and temperatures, and length of input and output.
- The more statements are processed, the more API calls are made, increasing the cost.
- The costs vary depending on the model used.
- Some models are more expensive than others (see <https://openai.com/api/pricing/>).
- If you want to use several models or temperatures at the same time, this increases the costs.
- Long statements or complex requests can cause higher costs.
- Longer inputs or outputs will also result in higher costs.
- It is very difficult to predict everything. Therefore, the cost calculation described here can only be considered a rough estimate. No guarantee is given for actual costs incurred.
- The complete execution of both templates with the example statements and default settings is currently estimated to cost approximately 5.7 cents (USD). More information can be found in step 0.3.2.
- Compared to traditional coding, the costs are manageable in my view and justified by the higher efficiency through enormous time savings.

0.3.2 Download and use the cost estimation template

- I have prepared a template to estimate the costs for creating and assigning inductive categories with OpenAI's GPT models (step 1 + step 2). You can find the cost estimation template here: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15292.24966>
- Please download the categorization cost calculator template (*file name: LAIC_costcalculator_template.py*). You may need to scroll down a bit to find the file.

- Create a folder on your computer where the template and future files will be saved. Do not save the cost calculator template and future files in a zip folder. Please save the template and future files in a regular folder on your computer. As an example, I've created a folder on the desktop named "LAIC". I will use this folder throughout the guide to store all necessary files.
- Open the file named LAIC_costcalculator_template.py with your preferred Python editor. To do this, you must open your Python Editor (e.g., by clicking on the desktop link or in the list of

your installed programs). If you use Visual Studio Code, do not open the file directly. Instead, please go to the upper left corner and click on the two-page symbol. Then click on the "Open Folder" button and select the entire folder where you stored the file "LAIC_costcalculator_template.py" that you have just downloaded. Click on "Open" (in German: "Öffnen"). Remember: Open the entire folder, not just an individual file! This is important even if there is only one file in the folder. For demonstration, I show you how I open the folder "LAIC" on my desktop (in German: "Schreibtisch") where I store all the files associated with this guide. Do not be confused that the screenshot contains German language. On your device, it will be displayed in the language you are using on your computer.

- You might encounter a message asking if you trust the files. Please confirm that you trust these files to proceed with the process. This message is not displayed to all users. For me, it only appeared on the Windows laptop, but not on the iMac. If you don't receive a warning, don't be confused and just carry on.

- All files from this folder (in my example, the folder is named LAIC) should now be displayed in the explorer section on the left. If you've completed the cost estimation, those files will also appear here. Click on "LAIC_costcalculator_template.py" in the explorer section to open the template.

- It is necessary to install a few pip packages beforehand. Open a new terminal. In Visual Studio Code, you can click on "Terminal" in the top left-hand corner. Then click on "New Terminal". A new terminal window will then open in the lower area. You can also open a new terminal later before each new command. While it's not required, this approach can always help you keep better track of your work. However, if no terminal is currently open, you will need to open one before being able to type something into it.

- Enter **pip3 install openai pandas openpyxl xlswriter tiktoken** in the terminal and press Enter. Typically, using pip install openai pandas openpyxl xlswriter tiktoken should suffice for installing Python packages. However, on certain operating systems, such as macOS and Linux, there might be multiple versions of Python installed. In such cases, using pip3 install instead of pip install ensures that the package is installed specifically for Python 3, making it more precise. While pip3 install openai pandas openpyxl xlswriter tiktoken should generally work in most scenarios, if for any reason it doesn't, you can try using pip install openai pandas openpyxl xlswriter tiktoken as an alternative. In general, however, I recommend pip3 install openai pandas openpyxl xlswriter tiktoken for most users because it is less error-prone.

- A lot of information will now appear in your terminal, indicating that the installation is in progress. Simply let it run until it completes. This may take a few moments.
- Once the installation is complete, the path where you saved the template will reappear, and you can enter new commands in the terminal, though this is not necessary at this stage. Because I saved all files in the "LAIC" folder, I see LAIC in the terminal. You will see the name of the place where you saved your files.

- If the packages are already installed, you'll see "Requirement already satisfied" in the terminal.

```

c:\clarissaarlinghaus@MacvonClarissa LAIC % pip install openal pandas openpyxl
Requirement already satisfied: openal in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (1.40.3)
Requirement already satisfied: pandas in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (2.2.2)
Requirement already satisfied: openpyxl in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (3.1.5)
Requirement already satisfied: anyio<5,>=3.5.0 in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (from openal) (4.4.0)
Requirement already satisfied: distro<2,>=1.7.0 in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (from openal) (1.3.0)
Requirement already satisfied: httpx<1,>=0.23.0 in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (from openal) (0.27.0)
Requirement already satisfied: jiter<1,>=0.4.0 in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (from openal) (0.5.0)
Requirement already satisfied: pydantic<3,>=1.9.0 in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (from openal) (2.8.2)
Requirement already satisfied: sniffio in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (from openal) (1.3.1)
Requirement already satisfied: tqdm<4 in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (from openal) (4.66.5)
Requirement already satisfied: typing-extensions<5,>=4.11 in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (from openal) (4.12.2)
Requirement already satisfied: numpy<=1.26.0 in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (from pandas) (2.0.1)
Requirement already satisfied: python-dateutil<=2.8.2 in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (from pandas) (2.9.0.post0)
Requirement already satisfied: pytz<=2020.1 in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (from pandas) (2024.11)
Requirement already satisfied: tzdata<=2022.7 in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (from pandas) (2024.1)
Requirement already satisfied: et-xmlfile in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (from openpyxl) (1.1.0)
Requirement already satisfied: idna<=2.8 in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (from anyio<5,>=3.5.0->openal) (3.7)
Requirement already satisfied: certifi in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (from httpx<1,>=0.23.0->openal) (2024.7.4)
Requirement already satisfied: httpcore<1,* in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (from httpx<1,>=0.23.0->openal) (1.0.5)
Requirement already satisfied: h11<0.15,>=0.13 in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (from httpcore<1,*->httpx<1,>=0.23.0->openal) (0.14.0)
Requirement already satisfied: annotated-types<=0.4.0 in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (from pydantic<3,>=1.9.0->openal) (0.7.0)
Requirement already satisfied: pydantic-core<=2.28.1 in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (from pydantic<3,>=1.9.0->openal) (2.28.1)
Requirement already satisfied: six<=1.5 in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (from python-dateutil<=2.8.2->pandas) (1.16.0)
c:\clarissaarlinghaus@MacvonClarissa LAIC %

```

- The template can only provide a valid cost estimate if you use the same statements, models, repetitions, and roles as later in step 1 and step 2. That is why we are now going through all these relevant factors step by step. Let's start with the statements.
- Define which statements shall be used to form inductive categories. I recommend entering them into a column in an Excel file and then referring to the Excel file in the Python template. I also prepared an Excel template file for you to put in your statements. You can find it here: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.31741.78564>

- Please save the Excel file in the folder with the other template. This way it will be better recognized by the Python template.
- It is worthwhile to complete the Excel template, as it will also be required for step 1 and step 2 of the LAIC method. Please delete the example statements (but not the heading "Statements") and enter all your statements into the Excel template. All statements must be listed one below the other in the "Statements" column. If you do not have any statements to be categorized and still want to test LAIC, you can also use the example sentences from the Excel template for statements.

	A
1	Statements
2	My favorite color is red.
3	I like to eat lasagna.
4	Blue is my favorite color.
5	I like yellow.
6	I could eat pizza every day!
7	I love green!
8	
9	
10	

- You probably already have a file with all your statements. If it is an Excel file in which all statements are in one column, it is sufficient to rename the column to "Statements" (without quotation marks) and adjust the name of the Excel file in line 15. Please ensure that the file extension .xlsx, as well as the single quotation marks (') before and after the file name, are preserved. If you have a different file format (e.g., Word document), you can copy your statements into my Excel template. All statements must be listed one below the other in the "Statements" column. If you save my Excel template under a new name, you must also update

line 15 with the new Excel file name. If you prefer not to name the column containing the statements "Statements", you need to specify the corresponding column name in line 19.

- If you used my template or named your file "statements.xlsx" with a column named "Statements", you can leave the template as it is.

```
13
14 # Load the Excel file and extract the statements
15 file_path = 'statements.xlsx' ← just the path accordingly
16 df = pd.read_excel(file_path)
17
18 # Assuming the statements are in a column named 'Statements'
19 statements = df['Statements'].dropna().tolist() ←
20 number_of_statements = len(statements)
21
```

- Since the costs depend on the model and the number of repetitions, these values need to be entered into the LAIC cost calculator template.
- Please specify which model you want to use in line 10. By default, this template uses gpt-4o-2024-05-13, just like the other templates. If you plan to use my other templates with gpt-4o-2024-05-13, you can leave this as it is. Please enter the cost for one million input tokens in line 28 and the cost for one million output tokens in line 29. I have used the current prices for gpt-4o-2024-05-13, but since prices can change or you may want to use a different model, I recommend checking OpenAI's Pricing page for the most up-to-date information (see <https://openai.com/api/pricing/>).
- Please specify in line 32 how many repetitions should be performed for the categorization template (step 1). Similarly, please specify in line 33 how many repetitions should be performed for the assignment template (step 2). If you intend to use both templates with the default settings (10 repetitions each), you can also leave the repetitions as they are.

```
6
7 # Function to calculate the number of tokens using tiktoken
8 def count_tokens(text):
9     # Initialize the encoder for the specific model you are using
10    encoder = tiktoken.encoding_for_model('gpt-4o-2024-05-13') ←
11    tokens = encoder.encode(text)
12    return len(tokens)
13
14 # Load the Excel file and extract the statements
15 file_path = 'statements.xlsx' # Adjust the path accordingly
16 df = pd.read_excel(file_path)
17
18 # Assuming the statements are in a column named 'Statements'
19 statements = df['Statements'].dropna().tolist()
20 number_of_statements = len(statements)
21
22 # Estimate the number of categories
23 # Rule of thumb: 1 category per 10 statements
24 estimated_categories = max(1, number_of_statements // 10)
25 categories = [f'category{i}' for i in range(1, estimated_categories + 1)]
26
27 # Parameters for cost calculation
28 price_per_million_input_tokens = 5.00 ← actual price for 1 million input tokens
29 price_per_million_output_tokens = 15.00 ← actual price for 1 million output tokens
30
31 # Number of repetitions
32 repetitions_template_1 = 10 ← actual number of repetitions
33 repetitions_template_2 = 10 ← actual number of repetitions
34
```

- The system role and user role also affect the costs. Therefore, these roles need to be specified in the template as well. If you use the default roles of step 1 and step 2, you don't need to make any changes because I have already entered them for you. If you want to use different roles, please adjust the system role for the categorization template (step 1) in line 36 and the user role for the categorization template (step 1) in line 37. Similarly, adjust the system role for the assignment template (step 2) in line 44 and the user role for the assignment template (step 2) in line 45.

```

34
35 # Token calculation for the first template (LAIC_categorization_template.py)
36 system_prompt_template_1 = 'You are a coding system for qualitative research'
37 user_prompt_template_1 = 'Please create categories for the following statements:' + json.dumps(statements)
38 input_tokens_template_1 = count_tokens(system_prompt_template_1) + count_tokens(user_prompt_template_1)
39 # Output tokens: estimated as double the input tokens times the number of repetitions
40 output_tokens_template_1 = input_tokens_template_1 * 2 * repetitions_template_1
41 total_tokens_template_1 = input_tokens_template_1 + output_tokens_template_1
42
43 # Token calculation for the second template (LAIC_assignment_template.py)
44 system_prompt_template_2 = 'You will assign categories to statements.'
45 input_tokens_template_2 = sum(count_tokens(f'Here is a statement: "{statement}" - Assign one of the following categories: {",".join(categories)}') for statement in statements)
46 # Output tokens: estimated as double the input tokens times the number of repetitions
47 output_tokens_template_2 = input_tokens_template_2 * 2 * repetitions_template_2
48 total_tokens_template_2 = input_tokens_template_2 + output_tokens_template_2
49

```

- The results will be saved as both an Excel file and a text file. By default, the files are named "cost_estimation_timestamp.xlsx" and "cost_estimation_timestamp.txt". If this is okay for you, you can leave it as is. However, you can change the name in line 81 and 85 if you prefer a different file name. Ensure that the extensions .xlsx and .txt are retained. Similarly, the single quotation marks (') before and after the file name should be preserved. I recommend using the same filename for both file formats, but you are not required to do so. You can also use different filenames.

```

80 })
81 excel_filename = f'cost_estimation_{current_date_for_filename}.xlsx'
82 results_df.to_excel(excel_filename, index=False)
83
84 # Save results to a TXT file with 5 decimal places
85 txt_filename = f'cost_estimation_{current_date_for_filename}.txt'
86 with open(txt_filename, 'w') as file:
87     file.write(f'Date and Time: {current_datetime}\n')

```

- Before starting the cost estimation, it is necessary to save the file. Please click on "File" and "Save".

- Now you can start the creation of inductive categories by entering **python LAIC_costcalculator_template.py** (Windows) or **python3 LAIC_costcalculator_template.py** (macOS) in the terminal and pressing Enter. If you have saved the Python code under a new name, you need to enter python new name.py (Windows) or python3 new name.py (macOS) in the terminal and press Enter. Example: python calculator.py

```

PROBLEMS OUTPUT DEBUG CONSOLE TERMINAL PORTS
clarissaarlinghaus@iMacvonClarissa LAIC % python3 LAIC_costcalculator_template.py

```

- As soon as the cost estimation has been carried out, "Calculations completed and saved" appears in the terminal.

```

PROBLEMS OUTPUT DEBUG CONSOLE TERMINAL PORTS zsh + -
clarissaarlinghaus@iMacvonClarissa LAIC % python3 LAIC_costcalculator_template.py
Calculations completed and saved in cost_estimation_20240822_143050.xlsx and cost_estimation_20240822_143050.txt.
clarissaarlinghaus@iMacvonClarissa LAIC %

```

- Please note that the cost calculation provided is just an estimate. While I believe it is a conservative estimate because my actual costs were lower, this might not be the case for everyone, which is why I opted for a cautious approach. Deviations are possible, and I do not assume liability for any resulting costs. The cost estimate itself does not incur any charges.
- You can now open the files to view the costs. The files are stored in the same folder as the LAIC cost calculation template. I have configured the template to provide detailed information on the estimated token consumption and the individual costs for template 1 (LAIC_categorization_template.py) and template 2 (LAIC_assignment_template.py). You do not need to sum anything up, as token consumption for both templates has already been summed up and displayed in the "Total Tokens" section and the total costs are already calculated and displayed in the "Total Cost" section. The complete execution of both templates with the example statements and default settings is currently estimated to cost approximately 5.7 cents (USD).

```

cost_estimation_20240822_143050.txt ×
cost_estimation_20240822_143050.txt
1 Date and Time: 2024-08-22 14:30:50
2 Token Template 1: 1176
3 Cost Template 1: 0.01708
4 Token Template 2: 2730
5 Cost Template 2: 0.03965
6 Total Tokens: 3906
7 Total Cost: 0.05673

```

Step 1: Creating Inductive Categories

The first step is to create inductive categories with an LLM. This guide explains how to do this with a Python template using OpenAI's GPT-4o model as an example, but other LLMs can also be used.

1.1 Download and open the LAIC categorization template

- Please download the LAIC categorization template (file name: LAIC_categorization_template.py) via this link: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.11189.69605>
You may need to scroll down a bit to find the file.

- If you have not done already, please create a folder on your computer where the template and future files will be saved. Do not save the LAIC template and future files in a zip folder. Please save the template and future files in a regular folder on your computer. As an example, I've created a folder on the desktop named "LAIC". I will use this folder throughout the guide to store all necessary files. If you have already created a folder for cost estimation, please add the template to that folder.
- Open the file named LAIC_categorization_template.py with your preferred Python editor. To do this, you must open your Python Editor (e.g., by clicking on the desktop link or in the list of your installed programs).
- If you performed the cost estimation recently and haven't closed Visual Studio Code in the meantime, the folder is likely still open. To prevent confusion, please close the LAIC cost calculation template. In Visual Studio Code, you can simply close files by clicking on the "x" next to the name.

- If you have not completed the cost estimation, or if it has been a while since you did so, or if you closed the editor in the meantime, the explorer section might be empty. In that case, you need to open the folder where all the files are located. If you use Visual Studio Code, do not open the file directly. Instead, please go to the upper left corner and click on the two-page symbol. Then click on the "Open Folder" button and select the entire folder where you stored

the file "LAIC_categorization_template.py" that you have just downloaded. Click on "Open" (in German: "Öffnen"). Remember: Open the entire folder, not just an individual file! This is important even if there is only one file in the folder. For demonstration, I show you how I open the folder "LAIC" on my desktop (in German: "Schreibtisch") where I store all the files associated with this guide. Do not be confused that the screenshot contains German language. On your device, it will be displayed in the language you are using on your computer.

- You might encounter a message asking if you trust the files. Please confirm that you trust these files to proceed with the process. This message is not displayed to all users. For me, it only appeared on the Windows laptop, but not on the iMac. If you don't receive a warning, don't be confused and just carry on.

- All files from this folder (in my example, the folder is named LAIC) should now be displayed in the explorer section on the left. If you've completed the cost estimation, those files will also appear here. Click on "LAIC_categorization_template.py" in the explorer section to open the template.

1.2 Install the required Python libraries

- It is necessary to install a few pip packages beforehand. If you recently performed the cost estimation and have not closed Visual Studio Code in the meantime, the packages should be already installed, and you can skip to section 1.3. If you installed the pip packages a while ago or have closed Visual Studio Code in the meantime, you may want to complete step 1.2 to ensure everything is set up correctly. If you have not installed the pip packages yet, you must complete step 1.2, as the template cannot be executed without it.
- Open a new terminal. In Visual Studio Code, you can click on "Terminal" in the top left-hand corner. Then click on "New Terminal". A new terminal window will then open in the lower area. You can also open a new terminal later before each new command. While it's not required, this approach can always help you keep better track of your work. However, if no terminal is currently open, you will need to open one before being able to type something into it.

- Enter **pip3 install openai pandas openpyxl xlswriter** in the terminal and press Enter. Typically, using pip install openai pandas openpyxl xlswriter should suffice for installing Python packages. However, on certain operating systems, such as macOS and Linux, there might be multiple versions of Python installed. In such cases, using pip3 install instead of pip install ensures that the package is installed specifically for Python 3, making it more precise. While pip3 install openai pandas openpyxl xlswriter should generally work in most scenarios, if for any reason it doesn't, you can try using pip install openai pandas openpyxl xlswriter as an alternative. In general, however, I recommend pip3 install openai pandas openpyxl xlswriter for most users because it is less error-prone.

- A lot of information will now appear in your terminal, indicating that the installation is in progress. Simply let it run until it completes. This may take a few moments.
- Once the installation is complete, the path where you saved the template will reappear, and you can enter new commands in the terminal, though this is not necessary at this stage. Because I saved all files in the "LAIC" folder, I see LAIC in the terminal. You will see the name of the place where you saved your files.

```

Using cached certifi-2024.7.4-py3-none-any.whl (162 kB)
Using cached h11-0.14.0-py3-none-any.whl (58 kB)
Installing collected packages: pytz, tzdata, typing-extensions, tqdm, sniffio, six, numpy, jiter, idna, h11, et-xmlfile,
distro, certifi, annotated-types, python-dateutil, pydantic-core, openpyxl, httpcore, anyio, pydantic, pandas,
httpx, openai
Successfully installed annotated-types-0.7.0 anyio-4.4.0 certifi-2024.7.4 distro-1.9.0 et-xmlfile-1.1.0 h11-0.14.0 h
ttpcore-1.0.5 httpx-0.27.0 idna-3.7 jiter-0.5.0 numpy-2.0.1 openai-1.40.1 openpyxl-3.1.5 pandas-2.2.2 pydantic-2.8.2
pydantic-core-2.20.1 python-dateutil-2.9.0.post0 pytz-2024.1 six-1.16.0 sniffio-1.3.1 tqdm-4.66.5 typing-extensions
-4.12.2 tzdata-2024.1
cclarissaarlinghaus@MacvonClarissa LAIC %

```

- If the packages are already installed, you'll see "Requirement already satisfied" in the terminal.

```

PROBLEMS OUTPUT DEBUG CONSOLE TERMINAL PORTS
cclarissaarlinghaus@MacvonClarissa LAIC % pip install openai pandas openpyxl
Requirement already satisfied: openai in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (1.40.3)
Requirement already satisfied: pandas in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (2.2.2)
Requirement already satisfied: openpyxl in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (3.1.5)
Requirement already satisfied: anyio<5, >=3.5.0 in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (from openai) (4.4.0)
Requirement already satisfied: distro<2, >=1.7.0 in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (from openai) (1.9.0)
Requirement already satisfied: httpx<1, >=0.23.0 in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (from openai) (0.27.0)
Requirement already satisfied: jiter<1, >=0.4.0 in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (from openai) (0.5.0)
Requirement already satisfied: pydantic<3, >=1.9.0 in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (from openai) (2.8.2)
Requirement already satisfied: sniffio in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (from openai) (1.3.1)
Requirement already satisfied: tqdm<4 in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (from openai) (4.66.5)
Requirement already satisfied: typing-extensions<5, >=4.11 in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (from openai) (4.12.2)
Requirement already satisfied: numpy<=1.26.0 in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (from pandas) (2.0.1)
Requirement already satisfied: python-dateutil<=2.8.2 in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (from pandas) (2.9.0.post0)
Requirement already satisfied: pytz<=2020.1 in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (from pandas) (2024.1)
Requirement already satisfied: tzdata<=2022.7 in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (from pandas) (2024.1)
Requirement already satisfied: et-xmlfile in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (from openpyxl) (1.1.0)
Requirement already satisfied: idna<=2.0 in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (from anyio<5, >=3.5.0->openai) (3.7)
Requirement already satisfied: httpcore<1, >=0.23.0->openai (2024.7.4)
Requirement already satisfied: httpx<1, >=0.23.0->openai (1.0.5)
Requirement already satisfied: h11<0.15, >=0.13 in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (from httpcore<1, >=0.23.0->openai) (0.14.0)
Requirement already satisfied: pydantic-core<=2.20.1 in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (from pydantic<3, >=1.9.0->openai) (0.7.8)
Requirement already satisfied: six<=1.5 in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (from python-dateutil<=2.8.2->pandas) (1.16.0)
cclarissaarlinghaus@MacvonClarissa LAIC %

```

1.3 Enter OpenAI API key

- To create inductive categories with LLMs from OpenAI (e.g., GPT-4o), you need an OpenAI API key. Step 0.2 explains how to get an OpenAI API key.
- Once you have obtained an OpenAI API key, please enter it in line 10 by replacing '123456789' with your own key. Note that '123456789' is just a placeholder, not a real key. Do not share your actual OpenAI API key, as others could use it to run AI models at your expense.
- When replacing '123456789' with your real OpenAI API key, ensure that you keep the single quotation marks (') at the beginning and at the end of your key.

```

8
9 # Personal API key
10 client = OpenAI(api_key='123456789')
11

```

1.4 Adjust models, temperatures, and repetitions

- You can adjust the models, temperatures, and number of repetitions according to your preferences.
- In the template, the LLM model gpt-4o-2024-05-13 is specified with a temperature of 0 and 10 repetitions. These settings have proven particularly effective in our evaluation study. Therefore, we recommend using them. However, you are free to choose other models, temperatures, or repetitions if you prefer.
- If you agree with our recommended settings, you can proceed to step 1.5. If you prefer different settings, you can adjust lines 13-15 accordingly.
- If you wish to make changes to the model, be sure to preserve the single quotation marks (') in the model specification. Example: models = ['gpt-4o-mini-2024-07-18']
- If you want to use multiple models or temperatures, separate the entries with a comma. Example: temperatures = [0, 0.5, 1]

```

12 # Define models, temperatures, and repetitions
13 models = ['gpt-4o-2024-05-13']
14 temperatures = [0]
15 repetitions = 10
16

```

1.5 Adjust roles

- The roles tell the LLM models what to do. You can adjust the system role and user role according to your preferences.
- In the template, the system role is specified as "You are a coding system for qualitative research". The user role is specified as "Please create categories for the following statements:". This is in line with our evaluation study. However, you are free to adjust it to your needs and e.g., request more detailed explanations for the created categories.
- If you agree with the default settings, you can proceed to step 1.6. If you prefer different roles, you can adjust lines 26 and 27 accordingly.

```

21
22 # Analyze statements to create categories
23 def analyze_statements(model, temperature, statements):
24     response = client.chat.completions.create(model=model,
25     messages=[
26         {"role": "system", "content": "You are a coding system for qualitative research"},
27         {"role": "user", "content": "Please create categories for the following statements:" + json.dumps(statements)}
28     ],
29     temperature=temperature)
30     return response.choices[0].message.content
31

```

1.6 Load statements

- Define which statements shall be used to form inductive categories.
- You could manually enter all statements into the template. However, this can be exhausting if you have many statements (e.g., from an online survey) that you want to categorize inductively. Therefore, I recommend entering them into a column in an Excel file and then referring to the Excel file in the Python template. I also prepared an Excel template file for you to put in your statements. You can find it here: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.31741.78564>

- Please save the Excel file in the folder with the other templates. This way it will be better recognized by the Python template.
- It is worthwhile to complete the Excel template, as it will also be required for step 2. Please delete the example statements (but not the heading "Statements") and enter all your

statements into the Excel template. All statements must be listed one below the other in the "Statements" column. If you do not have any statements to be categorized and still want to test LAIC, you can also use the example sentences from the Excel template for statements.

	A
1	Statements
2	My favorite color is red.
3	I like to eat lasagna.
4	Blue is my favorite color.
5	I like yellow.
6	I could eat pizza every day!
7	I love green!
8	
9	
10	

- You probably already have a file with all your statements. If it is an Excel file in which all statements are in one column, it is sufficient to rename the column to "Statements" (without quotation marks) and adjust the name of the Excel file in line 84. Please ensure that the file extension .xlsx, as well as the single quotation marks (') before and after the file name, are preserved. If you have a different file format (e.g., Word document), you can copy your statements into my Excel template. All statements must be listed one below the other in the "Statements" column. If you save my Excel template under a new name, you must also update line 84 with the new Excel file name. If you prefer not to name the column containing the statements 'Statements', you need to specify the corresponding column name in line 85.

```

82
83 # Main execution
84 excel_file_path = 'statements.xlsx'
85 statements = load_statements_from_excel(excel_file_path, 'Statements')
86

```


1.7 Adjust file names

- The results will be saved as both an Excel file and a text file. By default, the files are named "categorization_timestamp.xlsx"/ "categorization_timestamp.txt" for forming the categories and "categorization_categories_frequency_timestamp.xlsx"/ "categorization_categories_frequency_timestamp.txt" for counting the categories formed. If this is okay for you, you can leave it as it is and move to step 1.8.
- However, you can change the name in lines 113-116 if you prefer different file names. I recommend using the same filename for both file formats, but you are not required to do so. You can also use different filenames.
- Ensure that the extensions .xlsx and .txt are retained. Similarly, the single quotation marks (') before and after the file name should be preserved. I also recommend that you keep

{timestamp} in the name so that the files are saved with date and time.

```
110
111 # Save final results
112 timestamp = datetime.now().strftime('%Y-%m-%d_%H-%M-%S')
113 analysis_file_path = f'categorization_{timestamp}.txt'
114 analysis_excel_path = f'categorization_{timestamp}.xlsx'
115 count_file_path = f'categorization_categories_frequency_{timestamp}.txt'
116 count_excel_path = f'categorization_categories_frequency_{timestamp}.xlsx'
117 save_categorization_results(all_analysis_results, analysis_file_path, analysis_excel_path)
118 save_count_results(all_category_counts, count_file_path, count_excel_path)
119
```

1.8 Run the Python code

- Before starting the creation of inductive categories, it is necessary to save the file. Please click on "File" and "Save".

- Now you can start the creation of inductive categories by entering **python LAIC_categorization_template.py** (Windows) or **python3 LAIC_categorization_template.py** (macOS) in the terminal and pressing Enter. If you have saved the Python code under a new name, you need to enter python new name.py (Windows) or python3 new name.py (macOS) in the terminal and press Enter. Example: python categorization.py

- While the code is being executed, the terminal fills up with information. Simply let the process run until it is completed.
- Depending on your data amount, computer hardware, and internet connection, this can take a reasonable amount of time (e.g., 5-30 minutes for approximately 300 statements). Please wait patiently.
- As soon as the creation of categories has been carried out, "The files have been saved successfully." appears in the terminal.


```

#####
- I like to eat lasagna.
- "I could eat pizza every day!"

These categories help to organize the statements based on the themes of color preferences and food preferences.
The files have been saved successfully.
clarissaarlinghaus@iMacvonClarissa LAIC %
Ln 10, Col

```

1.9 Review the generated files

- After completing step 1.9 of this guide, you will receive two files in both .txt and .xlsx formats, resulting in four files in total. These files are provided in both formats to accommodate different user preferences. The content in files with the same name is identical, assuming you haven't changed the default settings. You can choose the format that works best for you.
- In the following, I will explain what each file contains. Please note that the file names mentioned here are based on the default names provided in the template. If you have changed any names during the process, please refer to your specific file names accordingly.
- *Categorization Files with Timestamp*: The files named categorization with a timestamp (e.g., categorization_2024-08-22_14-38-09.txt) provide a detailed record of which model, at what temperature, and during which repetition, generated specific categories. You may choose to review these files in detail to check whether the categories align with your expectations. These files are useful if you want to understand the process behind the categorization more thoroughly. This output can vary with each run. Don't be surprised if you see different results than in my example, even if you used the same sample sentences.

```

Date and Time: 2024-08-22 14:37:55
Model: gpt-4o-2024-05-13, Temperature: 0, Repetition: 1
Output:
Sure! Here are some potential categories for the given statements:

```

- ```

1. **Favorite Color**
- "My favorite color is red."
- "Blue is my favorite color."
- "I love green!"

2. **Color Preferences**
- "I like yellow."

3. **Food Preferences**
- "I like to eat lasagna."
- "I could eat pizza every day!"

```

These categories help to organize the statements based on the themes of color preferences and food preferences.

```

Date and Time: 2024-08-22 14:37:56
Model: gpt-4o-2024-05-13, Temperature: 0, Repetition: 2
Output:
Sure! Here are some potential categories for the given statements:

```

- ```

### Categories:

1. **Favorite Color**
- "My favorite color is red."
- "Blue is my favorite color."
- "I like yellow."
- "I love green!"

2. **Favorite Food**
- "I like to eat lasagna."
- "I could eat pizza every day!"

```

These categories help to organize the statements based on the themes of favorite colors and favorite foods.

```

Date and Time: 2024-08-22 14:37:58
Model: gpt-4o-2024-05-13, Temperature: 0, Repetition: 3
Output:
Sure! Here are some potential categories for the given statements:

```

- *Categorization Categories Frequency with Timestamp*: If you prefer to focus on the results rather than the process, you can directly open the file named categorization categories frequency with a timestamp (e.g., categorization_categories_frequency_2024-08-22_14-38-09.xlsx). These files list the generated categories, starting with the most frequent one. This output can vary with each run. Don't be surprised if you see different categories or frequencies than in my example, even if you used the same sample sentences.

	A	B	C
1	Date and Time	Category	Frequency
2	2024-08-22 14:38:09	Favorite Color	10
3	2024-08-22 14:38:09	Food Preferences	6
4	2024-08-22 14:38:09	Color Preferences	6
5	2024-08-22 14:38:09	Favorite Food	2
6	2024-08-22 14:38:09	Color Preference	2
7	2024-08-22 14:38:09	Food Preference	2
8	2024-08-22 14:38:09	Likes Specific Color	1
9			

1.10 Make up a final set of categories

- To finalize your set of categories, please open the Excel file named categorization categories frequency with a timestamp (e.g., categorization_categories_frequency_2024-08-22_14-38-09.xlsx). This is the file from the screenshot above, where you can see the frequency of the categories.
- Please go through the categories step by step, starting with the most frequent one. Keep the most frequent category in the Excel file unless it was incorrectly generated and does not fit your topic or research question at all. Only do this if it's clearly an error by the LLM, not to manipulate the results.
- Next, move on to the second most frequent category and check whether it represents a new aspect. If it does, keep it. If it is very similar to the previous one and covers the same concept, delete the row in the Excel file. This way, you can avoid duplicates, redundancies, and overlaps. Also, delete any row where the category makes no sense because it completely misses the topic. Only do this if it's clearly an error by the LLM, not to manipulate the results.
- Continue this process with each subsequent category, deciding whether to keep or delete each one.
- If two categories that cover the same aspect have the same frequency, you can choose the one that you find more suitable or relevant.
- Proceed step by step until you have finalized your set of categories. The final set should contain only distinct aspects, without any duplicates or redundancies.

	A	B	C
1	Date and Time	Category	Frequency
2	2024-08-22 14:38:09	Favorite Color	10
3	2024-08-22 14:38:09	Food Preferences	6
4			

- Please save the edited Excel file as categories.xlsx. You can save Excel files under a new name by clicking on "File", then "Save As", and entering the new name (please use the name "categories" so that the file will be saved as categories.xlsx).
- Ensure that you save the Excel file with the final categories in the same folder where you have stored the other files, such as the categorization template.
- We will use this file in step 2.

Step 2: Assigning Categories

After setting up the inductive categories, we will now assign them to our statements. The template will count the assigned categories across all statements, providing an overview of which themes are most frequently mentioned, and count the categories per statement to determine the final coding.

You can also use step 2 to assign different categories (e.g., deductive categories). However, this guide mentions inductive categories because inductive categories were created in step 1.

2.1 Download and open the LAIC assignment template

- Please download the LAIC categories assignment template (file name: LAIC_assignment_template.py) via this link: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21256.02567/1>
You may need to scroll down a bit to find the file.

- Please store the template in the same folder where you saved the LAIC categorization template and other files associated with this guide. If you have not yet created such a folder, you must do so now. Do not save the files in a zip folder. Please save them in a regular folder on your computer. As an example, I've created a folder on the desktop named "LAIC". I will use this folder throughout the guide to store all necessary files.
- Open the file named LAIC_assignment_template.py with your preferred Python editor. To do this, you must open your Python Editor (e.g., by clicking on the desktop link or in the list of your installed programs).
- If you performed the creation of inductive categories (step 1) recently and haven't closed Visual Studio Code in the meantime, the folder is likely still open. To prevent confusion, please close the LAIC categorization template. In Visual Studio Code, you can simply close files by clicking on the "x" next to the name.

- If you have not completed the creation of inductive categories (step 1), or if it has been a while since you did so, or if you closed the editor in the meantime, the explorer section might be

empty. In that case, you need to open the folder where all the files are located. If you use Visual Studio Code, do not open the file directly. Instead, please go to the upper left corner and click on the two-page symbol. Then click on the "Open Folder" button and select the entire folder where you stored the file "LAIC_categorization_template.py" that you have just downloaded. Click on "Open" (in German: "Öffnen"). Remember: Open the entire folder, not just an individual file! This is important even if there is only one file in the folder. For demonstration, I show you how I open the folder "LAIC" on my desktop (in German: "Schreibtisch") where I store all the files associated with this guide. Do not be confused that the screenshot contains German language. On your device, it will be displayed in the language you are using on your computer.

- You might encounter a message asking if you trust the files. Please confirm that you trust these files to proceed with the process. This message is not displayed to all users. For me, it only appeared on the Windows laptop, but not on the iMac. If you don't receive a warning, don't be confused and just carry on.

- All files from this folder (in my example, the folder is named LAIC) should now be displayed in the explorer section on the left. If you've completed the cost estimation and/or step 1, those files will also appear here. Click on "LAIC_categorization_template.py" in the explorer section to open the template.

2.2 Install the required Python libraries

- It is necessary to install a few pip packages beforehand. If you recently performed the cost estimation or step 1 and have not closed Visual Studio Code in the meantime, the packages should be already installed, and you can skip to section 2.3. If you installed the pip packages a while ago or have closed Visual Studio Code in the meantime, you may want to complete step 2.2 to ensure everything is set up correctly. If you have not installed the pip packages yet, you must complete step 2.2, as the template cannot be executed without it.
- Open a new terminal. In Visual Studio Code, you can click on "Terminal" in the top left-hand corner. Then click on "New Terminal". A new terminal window will then open in the lower area. You can also open a new terminal later before each new command. While it's not required, this approach can always help you keep better track of your work. However, if no terminal is currently open, you will need to open one before being able to type something into it.

- Enter **pip3 install openai pandas openpyxl xlswriter** in the terminal and press Enter. Typically, using pip install openai pandas openpyxl should suffice for installing Python packages. However, on certain operating systems, such as macOS and Linux, there might be multiple versions of Python installed. In such cases, using pip3 install instead of pip install ensures that the package is installed specifically for Python 3, making it more precise. While pip3 install openai pandas openpyxl xlswriter should generally work in most scenarios, if for any reason it doesn't, you can try using pip install openai pandas openpyxl xlswriter as an

alternative. In general, however, I recommend pip3 install openai pandas openpyxl xlswriter for most users because it is less error-prone.

```
PROBLEMS OUTPUT DEBUG CONSOLE TERMINAL PORTS  
o clarissaarlinghaus@iMacvonClarissa LAIC % pip3 install openai pandas openpyxl xlswriter
```

- o A lot of information will now appear in your terminal, indicating that the installation is in progress. Simply let it run until it completes. This may take a few moments.
- o Once the installation is complete, the path where you saved the template will reappear, and you can enter new commands in the terminal, though this is not necessary at this stage. Because I saved all files in the "LAIC" folder, I see LAIC in the terminal. You will see the name of the place where you saved your files.

```
using cacneo certifi-2024.7.4-pys-none-any.whl (162 kB)  
Using cached h11-0.14.0-py3-none-any.whl (58 kB)  
Installing collected packages: pytz, tzdata, typing-extensions, tqdm, sniffio, six, numpy, jiter, idna, h11, et-xmlfile, distro, certifi, annotated-types, python-dateutil, pydantic-core, openpyxl, httpcore, anyio, pydantic, pandas, httpx, openai  
Successfully installed annotated-types-0.7.0 anyio-4.4.0 certifi-2024.7.4 distro-1.9.0 et-xmlfile-1.1.0 h11-0.14.0 httpcore-1.0.5 httpx-0.27.0 idna-3.7 jiter-0.5.0 numpy-2.0.1 openai-1.40.1 openpyxl-3.1.5 pandas-2.2.2 pydantic-2.8.2 pydantic-core-2.20.1 python-dateutil-2.9.0.post0 pytz-2024.1 six-1.16.0 sniffio-1.3.1 tqdm-4.66.5 typing-extensions-4.12.2 tzdata-2024.1  
o clarissaarlinghaus@iMacvonClarissa LAIC %
```

- o If the packages are already installed, you'll see "Requirement already satisfied" in the terminal.

```
PROBLEMS OUTPUT DEBUG CONSOLE TERMINAL PORTS  
o clarissaarlinghaus@iMacvonClarissa LAIC % pip install openai pandas openpyxl  
Requirement already satisfied: openai in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (1.40.3)  
Requirement already satisfied: pandas in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (2.2.2)  
Requirement already satisfied: openpyxl in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (3.1.5)  
Requirement already satisfied: anyio<=3.5.0 in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (from openai) (4.4.0)  
Requirement already satisfied: distro<=1.7.0 in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (from openai) (1.9.0)  
Requirement already satisfied: httpx<=0.23.0 in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (from openai) (0.27.0)  
Requirement already satisfied: jiter<=0.4.0 in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (from openai) (0.5.0)  
Requirement already satisfied: pydantic<3, >=1.9.0 in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (from openai) (2.8.2)  
Requirement already satisfied: sniffio in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (from openai) (1.3.1)  
Requirement already satisfied: tqdm<=4 in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (from openai) (4.66.5)  
Requirement already satisfied: typing-extensions<=5, >=4.11 in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (from openai) (4.12.2)  
Requirement already satisfied: numpy<=1.26.0 in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (from pandas) (2.0.1)  
Requirement already satisfied: python-dateutil<=2.8.2 in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (from pandas) (2.9.0.post0)  
Requirement already satisfied: pytz<=2020.1 in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (from pandas) (2024.1)  
Requirement already satisfied: tzdata<=2022.7 in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (from pandas) (2024.1)  
Requirement already satisfied: et-xmlfile in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (from openpyxl) (1.1.0)  
Requirement already satisfied: idna<=2.8 in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (from anyio<=3.5.0->openai) (3.7)  
Requirement already satisfied: certifi in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (from httpx<=0.23.0->openai) (2024.7.4)  
Requirement already satisfied: httpcore<=1 in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (from httpx<=0.23.0->openai) (1.0.5)  
Requirement already satisfied: h11<=0.15, >=0.13 in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (from httpcore<=1, >=0.23.0->openai) (0.14.0)  
Requirement already satisfied: annotated-types<=0.4.0 in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (from pydantic<3, >=1.9.0->openai) (0.7.0)  
Requirement already satisfied: pydantic-core<=2.0.1 in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (from pydantic<3, >=1.9.0->openai) (2.20.1)  
Requirement already satisfied: six<=1.5 in /Library/Frameworks/Python.framework/Versions/3.12/lib/python3.12/site-packages (from python-dateutil<=2.8.2->pandas) (1.16.0)  
o clarissaarlinghaus@iMacvonClarissa LAIC %
```

2.3 Enter OpenAI API key

- o To assign categories with LLMs from OpenAI (e.g., GPT-4o), you need an OpenAI API key. Step 0.2 explains how to get an OpenAI API key.
- o Once you have obtained an OpenAI API key, please enter it in line 8 by replacing '123456789' with your own key. Note that '123456789' is just a placeholder, not a real key. Do not share your actual OpenAI API key, as others could use it to run AI models at your expense.
- o When replacing '123456789' with your real OpenAI API key, ensure that you keep the single quotation marks (') at the beginning and at the end of your key.

```
6  
7 # Personal API key  
8 client = OpenAI(api_key='123456789')  
9
```

2.4 Adjust models, temperatures, and repetitions

- You can adjust the models, temperatures, and number of repetitions according to your preferences.
- In the template, the LLM model gpt-4o-2024-05-13 is specified with a temperature of 0 and 10 repetitions. These settings have proven particularly effective in our evaluation study. Therefore, we recommend using them. However, you are free to choose other models, temperatures, or repetitions if you prefer.
- If you agree with our recommended settings, you can proceed to step 2.5. If you prefer different settings, you can adjust lines 130-132 accordingly.
- If you wish to make changes to the model, be sure to preserve the single quotation marks (') in the model specification. Example: models = ['gpt-3.5-turbo-0125']
- If you want to use multiple models or temperatures, separate the entries with a comma. Example: temperatures = [0, 0.5, 1]

```
128
129 # Define models, temperatures, and repetitions
130 models = ['gpt-4o-2024-05-13']
131 temperatures = [0]
132 repetitions = 10
133
```

2.5 Adjust roles

- The roles tell the LLM models what to do. You can adjust the system role and user role according to your preferences. In the template, the system role is specified as "You will assign categories to statements.". The user role is specified as "Here is a statement: \"{statement}\". Assign one of the following categories:". This is in line with our evaluation study. However, you are free to adjust it to your needs and e.g., request more detailed explanations for the created categories.
- If you agree with the default settings, you can proceed to step 2.6. If you prefer different roles, you can adjust lines 30 and 31 accordingly.

```
29 messages=[
30     {'role': 'system', 'content': 'You will assign categories to statements.'},
31     {'role': 'user', 'content': f'Here is a statement: \"{statement}\". Assign one of the following categories: {", ".join(categories)}.'}
32 ],
33 temperature=temperature
```

2.6 Load statements

- Define to which statements categories shall be assigned. You should use the same statements as in step 1.6.
- If you have already prepared an Excel file named "statements.xlsx" with all your statements in a column labeled "Statements", and it is saved in the same folder as the other files, you can proceed to step 2.7.
- If you have not yet prepared such a file, you need to do so now. Refer to step 1.6 for instructions and a template.
- If you have chosen to name your Excel file and/or column differently, please adjust the file name in line 122 and/or the column name in line 123 accordingly. Ensure that you keep the single quotation marks (') at the beginning and at the end.

```

121 # Main execution
122 excel_file_path = 'statements.xlsx' ←
123 categories_excel_path = 'categories.xlsx'
124 statements = load_statements_from_excel(excel_file_path, 'Statements') ←
125 categories = load_categories_from_excel(categories_excel_path)
126 all_analysis_results = []

```

2.7 Load categories

- Define which categories shall be assigned. You should use the same categories as finalized in step 1.9.
- If you have finalized a set of categories in step 1.9 and saved them in an Excel file named "categories.xls" with a column named "Category" that contains all your final categories, and it is saved in the same folder as the other files, you can proceed to step 2.8.
- If you have not yet prepared such a file, you need to do so now.
- Please enter all your categories in a single column in an Excel spreadsheet. Name the column 'Category' and save the file as 'categories.xlsx'. Ensure that this Excel file is saved in the same folder as all the other files.

Category
Favorite Color
Food Preferences

- If you have chosen to name your Excel file containing your categories differently, please adjust the file name in line 123.

```

122 excel_file_path = 'statements.xlsx'
123 categories_excel_path = 'categories.xlsx' ←
124 statements = load_statements_from_excel(excel_file_path, 'Statements')

```

2.8 Adjust file names

- The results will be saved as both an Excel file and a text file. By default, the files that give an overview how often the categories were assigned across all statements are named "assignment_overview_timestamp.xlsx"/ "assignment_overview_timestamp.txt", the files that show how each individual statement was categorized in each run are named "assignment_timestamp.xlsx"/ "assignment_timestamp.txt", and the files that show the final coding are named "assignment_statement_category_timestamp.xlsx"/ "assignment_statement_category_timestamp.txt". If this is okay for you, you can leave it as is and move to step 2.9.
- However, you can change the names in lines 177-182 if you prefer different file names. I recommend using the same filename for both file formats, but you are not required to do so. You can also use different filenames.

- Ensure that the extensions .xlsx and .txt are retained. Similarly, the single quotation marks (') before and after the file name should be preserved. I also recommend that you keep {timestamp} in the name so that the files are saved with date and time.

```

175 # Save final results
176 timestamp = datetime.datetime.now().strftime('%Y-%m-%d_%H-%M-%S')
177 analysis_file_path = f'assignment_{timestamp}.txt'
178 analysis_excel_path = f'assignment_{timestamp}.xlsx'
179 count_file_path = f'assignment_overview_{timestamp}.txt'
180 count_excel_path = f'assignment_overview_{timestamp}.xlsx'
181 statement_count_file_path = f'assignment_statement_category_{timestamp}.txt'
182 statement_count_excel_path = f'assignment_statement_category_{timestamp}.xlsx'
183

```

2.9 Run the Python code

- Before starting the assignment of categories, it is necessary to save the file. Please click on "File" and "Save".

- Now you can start the assignment of categories to statements by entering **python LAIC_assignment_template.py** (Windows) or **python3 LAIC_assignment_template.py** (macOS) in the terminal and pressing Enter. If you have saved the Python code under a new name, you need to enter python new name.py (Windows) or python3 new name.py (macOS) in the terminal and press Enter. Example: python assignment.py

- While the code is being executed, the terminal fills up with information. Simply let the process run until it is completed.
- Depending on your data amount, computer hardware, and internet connection, this can take a reasonable amount of time (e.g., 30-60 minutes for approximately 300 statements). Please wait patiently.
- As soon as the creation of categories has been carried out, "The files have been saved successfully." appears in the terminal.

```

-----
Assigning category to statement: I like to eat lasagna. using model: gpt-4o-2024-05-13
Assigning category to statement: Blue is my favorite color. using model: gpt-4o-2024-05-13
Assigning category to statement: I like yellow. using model: gpt-4o-2024-05-13
Assigning category to statement: I could eat pizza every day! using model: gpt-4o-2024-05-13
Assigning category to statement: I love green! using model: gpt-4o-2024-05-13
Saving categorization results to assignment_2024-08-22_14-44-57.txt and assignment_2024-08-22_14-44-57.xlsx
The files have been saved successfully.
clarissaarlinghaus@MacvonClarissa LAIC %
Ln 138, Col 69 Spaces: 4 UTF-8 LF Python

```

2.10 Review the generated files

- After completing step 2.9, you will receive several files in both .txt and .xlsx formats. These files are provided in both formats to accommodate different user preferences. The content in files with the same name is identical, assuming you haven't changed the default settings. You can choose the format that works best for you.
- In the following, I will explain what each file contains. Please note that the file names mentioned here are based on the default names provided in the template. If you have changed any names during the process, please refer to your specific file names accordingly.
- *Assignment Files with Timestamp*: These files (e.g., assignment_2024-08-22_14-44-57.xlsx) provide a detailed record of how each model, at different temperatures and repetitions, assigned categories to statements. If you wish, you can review every single step and examine how the categorization was performed. However, it is not necessary to do so unless you want to delve deeply into the process.

	A	B	C	D	E	F
1	Date and Time	Model	Temperature	Repetition	Statement	Assigned Category
2	2024-08-22 14:44:23	gpt-4o-2024-05-13		0	1 My favorite color is red.	Favorite Color
3	2024-08-22 14:44:23	gpt-4o-2024-05-13		0	1 I like to eat lasagna.	Food Preferences
4	2024-08-22 14:44:24	gpt-4o-2024-05-13		0	1 Blue is my favorite color.	Favorite Color
5	2024-08-22 14:44:24	gpt-4o-2024-05-13		0	1 I like yellow.	Favorite Color
6	2024-08-22 14:44:25	gpt-4o-2024-05-13		0	1 I could eat pizza every day!	Food Preferences
7	2024-08-22 14:44:25	gpt-4o-2024-05-13		0	1 I love green!	Favorite Color
8	2024-08-22 14:44:26	gpt-4o-2024-05-13		0	2 My favorite color is red.	Favorite Color
9	2024-08-22 14:44:26	gpt-4o-2024-05-13		0	2 I like to eat lasagna.	Food Preferences
10	2024-08-22 14:44:27	gpt-4o-2024-05-13		0	2 Blue is my favorite color.	Favorite Color
11	2024-08-22 14:44:27	gpt-4o-2024-05-13		0	2 I like yellow.	Favorite Color
12	2024-08-22 14:44:28	gpt-4o-2024-05-13		0	2 I could eat pizza every day!	Food Preferences
13	2024-08-22 14:44:29	gpt-4o-2024-05-13		0	2 I love green!	Favorite Color
14	2024-08-22 14:44:29	gpt-4o-2024-05-13		0	3 My favorite color is red.	Favorite Color
15	2024-08-22 14:44:30	gpt-4o-2024-05-13		0	3 I like to eat lasagna.	Food Preferences
16	2024-08-22 14:44:30	gpt-4o-2024-05-13		0	3 Blue is my favorite color.	Favorite Color

- *Assignment Statement Category Files with Timestamp*: These files (e.g., assignment_statement_category_2024-08-22_14-44-57.xlsx) offer a summary of all the runs. They include information on which model, temperature, and number of repetitions were used, resulting in a specified number of runs, which are also listed. You can see how each statement was categorized across all the runs. The "Category Counts" section shows how often each category was assigned to a particular statement. For example, in my case, every statement was consistently categorized the same way across all 10 runs. However, this consistency isn't always guaranteed. People often provide complex responses that may touch on multiple aspects (e.g., a statement mentioning both colors and food, such as "My favorite color is red, but I also love eating lasagna."). Such statements might lead to different categorizations, which you can observe in the "Category Counts" column. This allows you to identify any discrepancies

and review them further. The number of runs is treated as if each run were an individual coder, with the final category being the one most frequently chosen across all runs. It's similar to a voting process where the category with the most "votes" becomes the final categorization you may wish to use.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
1	Date and Time	Models	Temperatures	Repetitions	Runs	Statement	Category Counts	Final Category
2	2024-08-22 14:44:57	[gpt-4o-2024-05-13]	[0]	10	10	My favorite color is red.	{Favorite Color: 10, Food Preferences: 0}	Favorite Color
3	2024-08-22 14:44:57	[gpt-4o-2024-05-13]	[0]	10	10	I like to eat lasagna.	{Favorite Color: 0, Food Preferences: 10}	Food Preferences
4	2024-08-22 14:44:57	[gpt-4o-2024-05-13]	[0]	10	10	Blue is my favorite color.	{Favorite Color: 10, Food Preferences: 0}	Favorite Color
5	2024-08-22 14:44:57	[gpt-4o-2024-05-13]	[0]	10	10	I like yellow.	{Favorite Color: 0, Food Preferences: 0}	Favorite Color
6	2024-08-22 14:44:57	[gpt-4o-2024-05-13]	[0]	10	10	I could eat pizza every day!	{Favorite Color: 0, Food Preferences: 10}	Food Preferences
7	2024-08-22 14:44:57	[gpt-4o-2024-05-13]	[0]	10	10	I love green!	{Favorite Color: 10, Food Preferences: 0}	Favorite Color
8								
9								

- *Assignment Overview Files with Timestamp*: If you only need a general overview and don't want to review each individual statement, you can refer to the assignment overview files (e.g., assignment_overview_2024-08-22_14-44-57.xlsx). These files provide a summary of how often each category was mentioned across all statements. They also indicate which model, temperature, and number of repetitions were used, and how many runs resulted from those settings. The file lists the categories you've used, and under "Total", they show how often each category was mentioned across all runs. Since this number can lead to overestimation or distortion with many runs, it's divided by the number of runs to produce the "Adjusted" value. Additionally, you can see how often each category was selected as the final category.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
1	Date and Time	Models	Temperatures	Repetitions	Runs	Category	Total	Adjusted	Final Category
2	2024-08-22 14:44:57	[gpt-4o-2024-05-13]	[0]		10	10 Favorite Color	40	4	4
3	2024-08-22 14:44:57	[gpt-4o-2024-05-13]	[0]		10	10 Food Preferences	20	2	2
4									
5									

- In total, these three files (or six, counting both formats) give you a comprehensive view of how the categories were assigned.
- Congratulations! You have successfully categorized all statements using the LAIC method. I hope you are satisfied with the process and its results. If you are interested in more information about LAIC, feel free to check out the next page with related references.

References

Thank you for your interest in LAIC. For more information about LAIC, we invite you to read our manuscript, where we developed the method and compared it with conventional coding. The manuscript is not yet published but is available as a preprint. You are also welcome to review the preregistrations. The sources for the templates used in this guide are also listed. Feel free to also cite this step-by-step guide. It is listed as well. Everything is available open access under a CC-BY 4.0 license.

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